

MMFGO: A Multimodal and Multiview Cascaded Embedding Fusion Model for Protein Function Prediction

Chaolin Song^{a,b,c}, Yue Hu^{d,e}, Siyu Li^{a,b,c}, Xinhui Li^{d,e}, Yuyin Ma^{a,*}, Yurong Qian^{d,e,c,b,**} and Lei Deng^{a,f}

^a*School of Software, Xinjiang University, Urumqi, Xinjiang, 830091, China*

^b*Xinjiang Engineering Research Center of Big Data and Intelligent Software, Xinjiang University, Urumqi, Xinjiang, China*

^c*Key Laboratory of Software Engineering, Xinjiang University, Urumqi, Xinjiang, 830091, China*

^d*School of Computer Science and Technology, Xinjiang University, Urumqi, Xinjiang, 830046, China*

^e*Joint International Research Laboratory of Silk Road Multilingual Cognitive Computing, Xinjiang University, Urumqi, Xinjiang, 830046, China*

^f*School of Computer Science and Engineering, Central South University, Changsha, Hunan, 410083, China*

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ABSTRACT

Protein function prediction remains a core challenge in computational biology. Existing methods often rely on a single modality or on naive concatenation of multiple modalities, which fails to fully exploit cross-modal and multiview complementarity. To address this, we present MMFGO, a multimodal and multiview cascaded embedding fusion model that systematically exploits modality heterogeneity. MMFGO implements a cascaded embedding fusion framework. It proceeds in three stages: deep cohesion within homogeneous views, precise integration of similar modalities, and efficient cross-modal fusion. This yields tightly coupled, information-rich representations. The Multiview Hierarchical Interaction Fusion (MHIF) module strengthens intra-modality multiview interaction, while the progressive modal fusion architecture suppresses conflicts and amplifies complementarities across similar modalities. Across two datasets, MMFGO delivers leading performance, achieving an Fmax of 0.532 and a Precision of 0.555. The gains across multiple metrics substantiate its effectiveness and strong generalization, positioning MMFGO as a principled new paradigm for addressing multimodal data heterogeneity.

*Corresponding author.

**Corresponding author.

✉ mayuyin@xju.edu.cn (Y. Ma); qyr@xju.edu.cn (Y. Qian)

ORCID(s):

Table S1

Comparison of different models on the CAFA4 dataset.

Method	BP				MF				CC			
	Fmax	Recall	Precision	AUPR	Fmax	Recall	Precision	AUPR	Fmax	Recall	Precision	AUPR
naive	0.175	0.106	0.498	0.307	0.273	0.324	0.236	0.283	0.523	0.468	0.591	0.535
DeepGOplus	0.359	0.329	0.395	0.295	0.390	0.297	0.569	0.346	0.634	0.577	0.704	0.585
MSF-PFP	0.367	0.328	0.416	0.266	0.386	0.307	0.519	0.315	0.639	0.580	0.711	0.599
ATGO	0.421	0.386	0.463	0.339	0.461	0.363	0.632	0.405	0.640	0.589	0.700	0.596
MMSMAPlus	0.472	0.445	0.506	0.412	0.668	0.633	0.730	0.611	0.713	0.680	0.750	0.705
DeepFRI	0.487	0.466	0.511	0.444	0.687	0.645	0.735	0.642	0.727	0.699	0.759	0.722
PredGO	<u>0.505</u>	<u>0.483</u>	<u>0.531</u>	<u>0.463</u>	<u>0.704</u>	<u>0.666</u>	<u>0.748</u>	<u>0.683</u>	<u>0.733</u>	<u>0.705</u>	<u>0.764</u>	<u>0.741</u>
MMFGO	0.532	0.506	0.555	0.478	0.718	0.681	0.759	0.705	0.748	0.722	0.779	0.762

(*) Bold indicates optimal values, and underlining indicates suboptimal values.

Table S2

Results of ablation experiments for each modality.

Method	BP				MF				CC			
	Fmax	Recall	Precision	AUPR	Fmax	Recall	Precision	AUPR	Fmax	Recall	Precision	AUPR
SS8	0.361	0.374	0.352	0.265	0.419	0.360	0.502	0.345	0.639	0.596	0.690	0.590
SeqFusion	<u>0.524</u>	<u>0.498</u>	<u>0.553</u>	<u>0.462</u>	<u>0.706</u>	<u>0.673</u>	0.742	<u>0.681</u>	<u>0.738</u>	<u>0.707</u>	<u>0.773</u>	<u>0.744</u>
TextFusion	0.423	0.406	0.441	0.368	0.523	0.454	0.616	0.485	0.688	0.654	0.726	0.684
Structure	0.477	0.449	0.521	0.404	0.674	0.626	<u>0.747</u>	0.651	0.720	0.692	0.758	0.699
MMFGO	0.532	0.506	0.555	0.478	0.718	0.681	0.759	0.705	0.748	0.722	0.779	0.762

(*) Bold indicates optimal values, and underlining indicates suboptimal values.

Table S3

Ablation study of MHIF with different fusion modules (Sequence).

Method	BP				MF				CC			
	Fmax	Recall	Precision	AUPR	Fmax	Recall	Precision	AUPR	Fmax	Recall	Precision	AUPR
CAFm	0.415	0.397	0.434	0.361	0.511	0.445	0.600	0.463	0.688	0.661	0.718	0.679
DFF	0.400	0.390	0.411	0.336	0.494	0.429	0.582	0.443	0.678	0.645	0.715	0.661
CGA	0.391	0.397	0.384	0.327	0.464	0.414	0.527	0.408	0.663	0.618	0.715	0.639
MSC	0.357	0.380	0.337	0.264	0.408	0.366	0.461	0.335	0.632	0.605	0.662	0.579
AFF	0.412	0.398	0.427	0.359	0.496	0.413	0.622	0.440	0.685	0.656	0.717	0.670
MHIF	0.437	0.424	0.450	0.383	0.526	0.442	0.649	0.475	0.693	0.662	0.727	0.691

(*) Bold indicates the best value.

Figure S1: The heatmap illustrates the Fmax performance of GO cross-species functional annotation based on training, validation, and test data from six species. The three subplots in the first row show Fmax on BPO, MFO, and CCO for one-hot encoded sequences. The three subplots in the second row show Fmax on BPO, MFO, and CCO when fusing sequence multi-view features using the MHIF module. The three subplots in the third row show the percentage improvement in performance on BPO, MFO, and CCO (where MO denotes the enhancement effect of the MHIF module relative to one-hot encoding).

Figure S2: The heatmap illustrates the Fmax performance of GO cross-species functional annotation based on training, validation, and test data from six species. The three subplots in the first row show the Fmax scores on BPO, MFO, and CCO for biomedical literature encoded by BioBERT. The three subplots in the second row display the Fmax scores on BPO, MFO, and CCO when fusing multi-perspective features of biomedical literature using the MHIF module. The three subplots in the third row respectively show the percentage improvement in performance on BPO, MFO, and CCO (where MB denotes the enhancement effect of the MHIF module relative to BioBERT).

Figure S3: The heatmap illustrates the Fmax performance of GO cross-species functional annotation based on training, validation, and test data from six species. The three subplots in the first row show the Fmax of one-hot encoded biomedical literature on BPO, MFO, and CCO, respectively. The three subplots in the second row demonstrate the Fmax of fusing multi-view features from biomedical literature using the MHIF module on BPO, MFO, and CCO, respectively. The three subplots in the third row respectively show the percentage improvement in performance on BPO, MFO, and CCO (where MO denotes the enhancement effect of the MHIF module relative to one-hot encoding).